

Industrial Application of Fats and Oils in Presence of Water with Special Reference to the Thermodynamic Stability of Solubilized Solutions

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Solubilization of fats and oils in water has been studied by specific conductivity, transmission calorimetric and phase rule medicinal measurements at 40° and it is observed that solubilized solution (mustard oil + water) are not permanently thermodynamically stable even in presence of detergents and soaps and hence unsuitable for industrial, medicinal use due to toxicological effect.

SINCE solubilized solutions of oils are important for food, medicine and paints etc, an attempt has been made to study their stability.

Von Buzogh and others¹ have regarded colloids, emulsions and solubilized solutions as thermodynamically unstable while McBain² and his associates expressed contrary opinion indicating that they were as stable as the solutions of sugar in water.

Recently Chatterji³, the author⁴⁻¹¹ and Winsor¹² have reviewed all the theories and pointed out that there is a need of active consideration about the stability of solubilized solutions. Hence a number of properties e. g. electrical conductivity, transmission and calorimetry and phase rule of these solubilized solutions of oils in presence of soaps (Sodium Stearate) were studied in the concentration range of 1×10^{-6} % to 1×10^{-1} % to test their homogeneity, stability and the results have been discussed.

Material Used

Sodium stearate, mustard oil, HCl and specially prepared conductivity water.

Procedure : Aqueous mustard oil and soap solutions were prepared separately in the concentration range 1×10^{-6} % to 1×10^{-1} % at 40°, their solubilized solutions were also prepared⁴ and the above properties were studied.

Apparatus :

(1) **Conductivity bridge :** Specific conductivity of the two binary and a ternary system was measured by a conductivity bridge 'Leeds and Northrup type' at 40° using electromagnetic radiation method¹³.

(2) **Spectrophotometer :** Transmission was measured by sp. 600 unicamp make spectrophotometer at 40° in both the binary systems water + sodium stearate water + mustard oil against the wave length from 700 Å to 200 Å in order to select a common wave length (maxima) to study the absorption in the ternary system

which is obtained by mixing the two binary systems. Unfortunately instead of a common maxima, a common minima ($\lambda=530$) was obtained. This common minima was found suitable to study the changes in the ternary system though the change may not be greater than the changes, observed by selecting a common maxima which is not possible here.

Results

(a) **Conductivity measurements :** It is observed from the table 1 that log specific conductivity decreased from log 5.1634 to log 3.9743 in the log concentration range 6.4829 to 4.4829 in aqueous sodium stearate system. It increased again after a sudden fall but with a different slope on increasing the concentration further. When log specific conductivity was plotted against log concentration a straight line was obtained when the concentration of the detergent was increased beyond c.m.c., a straight line having a different slope was obtained Fig. 1a.

When the aqueous mustard oil solution was taken in the conductivity cell at very low concentration, the resistance of the solution could not be measured due to lack of a fine apparatus. On increasing the concentration of the oil further, log specific conductivity decreased continuously i. e. from log 6.7841 to 8.8244

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in the log concentration range $\bar{5}.4829$ to $\bar{3}.4826$. On plotting log specific conductivity (λ) versus log concentration it decreased again and followed a curve (Fig. 1b λ). These values were high as the mustard oil was impure though it was purified as far as possible by usual methods.

When both the binary mixtures were mixed together in equimolar ratio a ternary solubilized system was obtained. In this case specific conductivity, first decreased in the log concentration range $\bar{6}.4829$ to $\bar{5}.4372$ and then increased upto the log concentration $\bar{4}.4372$. Then there was a sharp fall at log concentration $\bar{4}.4829$ after which λ increased in the entire range (Table 1).

concentration range. When a graph was plotted, it is seen that transmission first decreased slightly and then sharply (Fig. 1a tr) in case of aqueous sodium stearate system while for the other, it decreased first (Fig. 1B tr), then there was a sharp break in the curve (c. m. c.). On increasing the concentration further, transmission decreased further on a straight line, but in case of the ternary system, it is seen that transmission first decreased from 97.47 to 82.32%, then increased to 96.32 % and was constant upto log concentration $\bar{4}.4372$ and finally it decreased.

When percentage transmission was plotted against log concentration (fig. IC tr), transmission decreased, attained a minimum value at log concentration $\bar{5}.4829$;

TABLE I—SPECIFIC CONDUCTANCE IN $\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{Cm}^{-1}$ TRANSMISSION IN PERCENTAGE AT 40° .

Systems Component Properties. Log. % conc**	Binary (Solutions)				Ternary (Solubilized Solutions)	
	Sodium Stearate+water		Mustard oil+water		Sodium Stearate+ Water+Mustard Oil	
	Log Specific Conductance II	Transmi- ssion III	Log Specific Conductance IV	Transmi- ssion V	Log Specific Conductance VI	Transmission VII
6.4829	$\bar{5}.1634$	92.78	—	97.14	$\bar{6}.0518$	97.45
6.9601	$\bar{5}.1643$	92.78	—	97.13	$\bar{5}.0727$	96.35
5.188	$\bar{5}.1785$	92.67	—	97.12	$\bar{5}.0378$	96.32
5.3280	$\bar{4}.9237$	92.67	—	97.11	$\bar{5}.2693$	96.12
5.4372	$\bar{4}.2746$	92.34	—	97.10	$\bar{5}.8311$	90.11
5.4829	$\bar{4}.0265$	92.34	$\bar{6}.1243$	97.00	$\bar{4}.7881$	81.32
5.9601	$\bar{4}.0211$	92.11	$\bar{6}.7841$	97.00	$\bar{4}.3489$	96.32
4.3282	$\bar{4}.0221$	92.00	$\bar{6}.8543$	97.00	$\bar{4}.3121$	96.32
4.4372	$\bar{3}.9042$	92.00	$\bar{6}.9244$	96.51	$\bar{3}.9713$	96.32
4.4829	$\bar{3}.9743$	92.00	$\bar{7}.0132$	95.15	$\bar{5}.2163$	92.52
4.9601	$\bar{3}.4041$	91.90	$\bar{7}.1913$	94.34	$\bar{3}.5632$	83.12
3.2095	$\bar{3}.3934$	91.86	$\bar{7}.3567$	90.00	$\bar{3}.4641$	78.51
3.4372	$\bar{3}.3502$	96.50	$\bar{7}.8546$	86.43	—	78.36
3.9829	$\bar{2}.6949$	84.40	$\bar{8}.1472$	86.41	$\bar{2}.8633$	72.66
2.2096	$\bar{2}.5238$	54.62	$\bar{8}.2272$	86.14	$\bar{2}.7643$	71.66
2.4372	$\bar{2}.5663$	44.32	$\bar{8}.6273$	86.41	$\bar{2}.4003$	48.62
2.4829	$\bar{2}.5024$	36.51	$\bar{8}.6573$	86.12	$\bar{2}.1876$	31.16
2.9601	$\bar{2}.5006$	14.92	$\bar{8}.8244$	81.22	$\bar{2}.0742$	26.47

Conc. of sod. stearate as given in column I. **Log concentrations in percentage.

When λ was plotted against log concentration, λ attained a maximum value at log concentration $\bar{5}.3280$ and then decreased. On increasing the concentration further, another maxima was obtained after which λ decreased to a minimum value at log conc. $\bar{4}.4829$. On increasing the concentration further, λ increased again. Thus two maxima were obtained. Suggesting that clusters assembled at the two peaks, the first in the very low region due to adsorption and the other due to assemblance of micelles near c.m.c. making the solution heterogeneous and unstable. The increase of conductivity was a clear sign that the particle size started growing for the separation of the phases in the solution.

Transmission measurements : Since a change in electrical conductivity pointed out the growth of the particle, it was necessary to observe the changes by some optical method using a spectrophotometer. From the Table 1, it is observed that transmission decreased continuously from 92.78 to 14.91 % and 97.14 to 81.2 % in both the respective binary systems in the entire

on increasing the concentration further, transmission after an increase, attained a minima again at log concentration $\bar{4}.4829$. On increasing the concentration further, a sharp fall in transmission was noticed at $3.03 \times 10^{-2} M$. These two minima occurred almost at the same concentrations which were obtained by conductivity measurements suggesting that near two concentration ranges the behaviour of the solubilized solution was quite different from the rest of the region. It is to be noted that the formation of liquid crystal in case of sodium stearate may not affect the result much due to high temperature ($40^\circ C$) and low concentration of the system investigated.

(3). **Calorimetric Measurements :** By potentiometric-thermister assembly, the heat of solubilization was measured in a platinum calorimeter. It was observed that the heat of solubilization curve followed the conductivity curve showing that maximum heat was liberated at two peaks, due to interaction of clusters.

(4). *Phase rules* : In the binary system, number of phases and components were 2 and 2 respectively and the degree of freedom was again '2' i.e.,

$$F = C - P + 2 = 2 - 2 + 2 = 2$$

Now it is obvious that the properties of such solutions depended on concentration and temperature. When they were plotted, regular changes were observed in binaries. On mixing the two binary systems for obtaining a ternary system the degree of freedom 'F' again came out to be ,

$$F = C - P + 2 = 3 - 3 + 2 = 2$$

This means that the behaviour of binary and ternary mixtures should not vary provided that there is no interaction between the molecules, but in actual practice, two peaks were obtained. Solubilized mixture behaved indifferently due to cluster formation. Such loose combination of molecules are formed between hexamethyl benzene and choramil¹¹⁻²¹. When the concentration of the detergent increased, the solution broke into its components, making these solutions. heterogeneous and thermodynamically unstable. (1-13)(14-26). and hence unsuitable for industrial and medicinal use due to toxicological effect.

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